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Novel strategies for septic shock management

(based on current guidelines and
research)

Dr. Gandhi B. Pathrudu ;
Dr. Dnyanesh M. Belekar
Dept of General Surgery

**Terna Medical College & Hospital,
Nerul, Navi Mumbai.**

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Abstract

- **Background:** Septic shock remains a leading cause of mortality despite advances in critical care. Recent updates and guidelines have shifted clinical approaches to improve recognition and management. This review highlights the role of various clinical tools, interventions, and therapeutic strategies in managing septic shock.
- **Objective:** To examine the current clinical strategies and guidelines in recognizing and treating septic shock, with emphasis on occult septic shock, fluid resuscitation, vasopressor usage, and the role of steroids, lactate monitoring, and procalcitonin in prognosis.
- **Methods:** A comprehensive review of the literature, including the latest guidelines from the Third International Consensus Definitions for Sepsis and Septic Shock (Sepsis-3), the Surviving Sepsis Campaign, and retrospective studies comparing clinical tools such as SIRS, qSOFA, and NEWS for early identification of septic shock.
- **Results:** 1. Recognition of Septic Shock: - SIRS, qSOFA, and NEWS were evaluated, with NEWS emerging as a more accurate tool for early recognition. - Lactate and procalcitonin are valuable markers but have limitations in predicting patient outcomes. 2. Resuscitation Strategies: - Ringer's Lactate is preferred over saline for initial resuscitation due to the latter's association with hyperchloremic acidosis. - The recommended fluid resuscitation strategy includes rapid administration of 30mL/kg crystalloid for hypotension or lactate > 4 mmol/L. 3. Vasopressor and Steroid Use: - Early norepinephrine administration is recommended to maintain a MAP > 65 mmHg. - Vasopressin is the second-line vasopressor, though its benefits in reducing mortality are uncertain. - Steroids, particularly in conjunction with vitamin C and thiamine, may improve outcomes in vasopressor-refractory septic shock. 4. Antibiotic Timing and Administration: - Early antibiotic administration, ideally within one hour of sepsis diagnosis, significantly improves survival rates.
- **Conclusion:** Effective management of septic shock involves early recognition using appropriate clinical tools like NEWS, aggressive fluid resuscitation with balanced crystalloids, timely initiation of vasopressors, and careful consideration of steroids and antibiotics. Further large-scale randomized controlled trials are needed to refine these approaches, particularly in vasopressor and steroid administration.
- **Keywords:** Septic shock, SIRS, qSOFA, NEWS, lactate, procalcitonin, norepinephrine, vasopressin, fluid resuscitation, antibiotics.

Introduction

- Septic shock has highly mortality rate.
- Mortality approaches 30% despite advances in critical care research in the last few decades.
- This review discusses on how to recognize occult septic shock,
- role of SIRS, qSOFA and NEWS for predicting poor outcomes in septic patients,
- type of fluid quantity and best fluid for resuscitation of the septic shock patients,
- indications for norepinephrine, and timing, goals of resuscitation in the patient with septic shock,
- timing of antibiotics administration,

Introduction

Indications for a second vasopressor after norepinephrine,

indications for steroids,

Role of steroids with Vitamin C and thiamine for patients in septic shock,

pitfalls of lactate interpretation.

How serial lactates compare to capillary refill in predicting poor outcomes,

role of procalcitonin as a prognostic indicator in septic patients,

the value of IVC girth and collapsibility for guiding fluid management in septic shock

The latest definitions of sepsis and septic shock

- As per the Third International Consensus Definitions for Sepsis and Septic Shock [1]:
- Sepsis is "life-threatening organ dysfunction caused by a dysregulated host response to infection" with a SOFA score >2 .
- Septic shock is "a subset of sepsis in which particularly profound circulatory, cellular, and metabolic abnormalities are associated with a greater risk of mortality than with sepsis alone", identified clinically by a vasopressor requirement to maintain a MAP > 65 and serum lactate > 2 mmol/L in the absence of hypovolemia.

What is sepsis ?

“We therefore propose the phrase *systemic inflammatory response syndrome* (SIRS) to describe this inflammatory process...”

Definition of
Sepsis
published in
CHEST

SIRS when 2 or more of the following criteria met:

- (1) Temperature > 38°C or < 36 °C
- (2) Heart rate >90
- (3) Respiratory rate >20 or PaCO₂ <32

SIRS + Infection = Sepsis

Quick SOFA criteria (qSOFA)

- Respiratory rate ≥ 22 /min •
 - Altered mentation •
 - Systolic blood pressure ≤ 100 mm Hg
-
- Non-ICU patients with qSOFA = 2-3 are at increased risk of death or prolonged ICU stay (> 3 days)

National Early Warning Score (NEWS)

Physiological Parameters	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	NEWS Scores	Clinical Risk
Respiration Rate (BPM)	≤8		9-11	12-20		21-24	≥25	0 Aggregate 1 - 4	Low
Oxygen Saturations (%)	≤91	92-93	94-95	≥96					
Any Supplemental Oxygen		Yes		No				RED Score* (Individual parameter scoring 3) Aggregate 5 - 6	Medium
Temperature (°C)	≤35		35.1-36.0	36.1-38.0	38.1-39.0	≥39.1			
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	≤90	19-100	101-110	111-219			≥220	Aggregate 7 or more	High
Heart Rate (BPM)	≤40		41-50	51-90	91-110	111-130	≥131		
Level of Consciousness				A			V, P or U		

What is the best clinical tool to aid in the recognition of sepsis and septic shock?

A recent retrospective study compared the clinical tools SIRS, qSOFA, and NEWS (National Early Warning Score) for the early identification of sepsis in the ED, and found that NEWS was more accurate than both SIRS and qSOFA for the early recognition of septic shock [2]

The beauty of the NEWS is that it can be calculated at triage without the need for blood test results and it allows for improved risk stratification

Lab tests in the early management of sepsis and septic shock

- Lactate as a diagnostic marker for sepsis and septic shock
- If you are still unsure if your patient is septic or not after calculating the NEWS, obtain a serum lactate early.
- lactate is useful to help identify occult septic shock in those patients who don't present in florid septic shock, but it is very nonspecific

Procalcitonin as a diagnostic marker for sepsis and septic shock

- A meta-analysis from 2015 suggested that procalcitonin levels in early stages of sepsis are significantly lower among survivors as compared with nonsurvivors of sepsis [4].
- However, a more recent retrospective study using the Sepsis-3 definition outlined above, found that procalcitonin has low sensitivity and specificity.
- Other studies suggest that procalcitonin may help risk stratify pneumonia and guide antibiotic de-escalation, but its use in sepsis in the ED is probably not very helpful.

Resuscitation fluid of choice in sepsis and septic shock

- **SALT-ED trial**

the saline group had a significantly higher 30 day composite of death, dialysis or creatinine >200% from baseline[6].

- **SMART trial**

septic patients who received saline had a higher mortality rate (29% vs 25%) compared to those who received balanced solutions (Ringer's or Plasmalyte) [7].

- Experts recommend Ringer's Lactate as the initial resuscitation fluid of choice in sepsis and septic shock because

- normal saline is thought to be associated with worsening

- hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis [8] as well as

- renal vasoconstriction from the chloride load resulting in poor renal function [9]

Endpoint of resuscitation: How much fluid should be given up front in sepsis and septic shock?

- There is The Surviving Sepsis Campaign 2018 Update [10] suggests starting a rapid administration of 30mL/kg crystalloid for patients with hypotension or a lactate > 4,
- Canadian Guidelines from 2008 suggest "an initial bolus of 1-2 L of crystalloid or 500-1000 mL of colloid should be given over 30-60 minutes and repeated as required to correct tissue perfusion and/or blood pressure abnormalities." [11].
- In practice, some patients will only need 1 litre, others will require 5. Titrate your fluids to the individual. initial fluid resuscitation should be enough to keep the MAP > 65 while endorgan perfusion is maintained (adequate urine output, level of awareness, capillary refill and decreasing lactate
- **IVC width and collapsability**[15] are other measures that can aid in the determination of whether or not a patient with sepsis has been adequately volume resuscitated, but should not be used alone in this determination.

Endpoint of resuscitation: Lactate clearance vs Capillary refill time normalization

- The 2019 ANDROMEDA-SHOCK RCT of 424 patients with septic shock compared normalization of Lactate vs normalization of capillary refill time in the resuscitation of patients with septic shock [16].
- Using lactate clearance resulted in more fluid administered, more vasopressors and more epinephrine without any significant
- improvement in outcomes. There was a trend toward higher 28-day mortality in the lactate clearance group (35% in the capillary refill time group vs 43% in the lactate clearance group),
- **Procalcitonin clearance** has also been studied [17]. A prospective, observational cohort ICU study of patients with severe sepsis and septic shock found that 24- and 48-hour procalcitonin clearance scores were significantly higher in survivors.

Starting norepinephrine in sepsis and septic shock: Is earlier better?

- Probably. The Surviving Sepsis Campaign 2018 Update suggests starting norepinephrine if the patient is hypotensive *during or after* fluid resuscitation to maintain a MAP > 65. There is no need to wait for 2-3L of crystalloid to go in.
- A more recent study, CENSER, is the first ever prospective randomized trial looking at vasopressors in sepsis.
- Mortality was lower in the early norepinephrine group (16% vs 22%) but not statistically significant. This study is consistent with previous data that suggests that early initiation of norepinephrine in septic shock is preferable, although large RCTs are pending.
- Currently, the CLOVERS trial [19] is underway comparing early vasopressors to IV fluid resuscitation.
- **Dosing norepinephrine in septic shock**
- Start at 5 mcg/min and titrate immediately after each q5minute BP check. This will likely require you to stay at the bedside.
- *Note* that a radial arterial line may underestimate MAP compared to a femoral arterial line by as much as 5 mmHg in early septic shock and >5 in advanced shock, leading to higher doses of norepinephrine than are necessary. [20]

Vasopressin is the second line vasopressor in septic shock

- **Vasopressin reduces the need for norepinephrine but does not reduce mortality**
- **The VANISH study suggested that while early vasopressin does maintain blood pressure and reduce the requirement for norepinephrine and renal replacement therapy, it does not reduce the number of renal replacement free days or mortality rate [21].**
- **The VASST study did not show a mortality benefit from adding vasopressin if the MAP was adequately maintained with norepinephrine [22].**
- **When should vasopressin be initiated in septic shock?**
- **There is no clear evidence for the indications for starting vasopressin in patients with septic shock. Our expert recommends starting vasopressin when moderate doses of norepinephrine (as in 0.5 mcg/kg/min or 35 mcg/min) have been reached.**

Antibiotic timing, administration and choice in sepsis and septic shock

- **Timing of antibiotic administration in sepsis and septic shock**
- We know that with each passing hour that antibiotics are *not* initiated in septic shock, survival drops - it's a time bomb.
- the newest Surviving Sepsis Campaign Guidelines to mandate antibiotics within the
- 1st hour of the patient hitting triage for anyone suspected of sepsis as part of their Sepsis Management Bundle [10].
- Rather than aiming for antibiotic administration within 1 hour of arrival at the ED, expert recommends to aim for antibiotic administration *within 1 hour of the diagnosis being made*.
- **How fast should antibiotics be given in sepsis and septic shock? We use push dose pressors - why not push dose antibiotics?**
- Once the decision to give IV antibiotics has been made they should be given over 5 minutes (rather than the usual 30 minutes) in order to reach peak effect as early as possible. The exception is vancomycin which must be given slowly.
- **Give the most important antibiotic first, and consider administering the second antibiotic orally at the same time as the IV antibiotic if the second antibiotic has excellent bioavailability (e.g. cephalexin, ciprofloxacin, doxycycline etc).**
- **Which antibiotics are best for sepsis without an apparent source?**
- Inappropriate antibiotic choice decreases survival in sepsis [24]. So it is important to choose your antibiotics wisely based on local antibiograms.
- search for the source of infection early. Chest, urine, abdomen are #1, #2 and #3 of sources of infection that are not immediately obvious on clinical exam.

What are the indications for steroids in septic shock?

- There has been much conflicting evidence for the benefit of steroids in septic shock.
- ADRENAL
 - outcomes of shock reversal, ventilator free days, LOS in the ICU, and fewer blood transfusions required improved in the hydrocortisone group.
- APROCCHSS
 - (Activated Protein C and Corticosteroids for Human Septic Shock) trial
 - 90 day mortality which was 43% in the hydrocortisone group vs 49% in the placebo group. These patients were sicker than the patients in the ADRENAL trial.
 - In other words, beneficial effects may only be seen in those patients with the highest illness severity scores.
- **Bottom line:** Although the evidence is mixed as to whether or not steroids are beneficial in septic shock, our expert recommends administering steroids for:
 - Vasopressor refractory shock (i.e. patient remains in shock despite norepinephrine 0.5mcg/kg/min)
 - Patients who are taking steroid medications at baseline
 - Patients with concomitant adrenal suppression
 - Another recent study looked at mortality rates among patient with septic shock who received thiamine, steroids and vitamin C .
 - Mortality was 8.5% in those treated with the cocktail of all 3 medications vs 40% in those not.

Take home points on sepsis and septic shock

- Calculate NEWS to detect subtle cases of occult septic shock.
- Less saline, more Ringer's, even if acute heart failure, especially in renal failure and severe acidosis.
- Norepinephrine whenever MAP <65 – earlier rather than later.
- Early antibiotics (within 1hr of the *diagnosis* rather than 1 hour of arrival at ED), given over 5 minutes (except vancomycin over 30 minutes), chosen wisely according to local antibiograms

Take home points on sepsis and septic shock

- Use a combination of MAP, GCS, urine output, initial lactate, capillary refill time, POCUS IVC to guide initial fluid resuscitation, individualized to each patient.
- If the lactate is rising despite resuscitative efforts call your intensivist. Early to ICU is preferable, but remember that capillary refill time may be as good, or even better than lactate at guiding resuscitation.
- Consider vasopressin and hydrocortisone if a MAP of 65 cannot be maintained with 35mcg/min norepinephrine and ongoing fluid resuscitation.

References

- Singer M, Deutschman CS, Seymour CW, et al. The Third International Consensus Definitions for Sepsis and Septic Shock (Sepsis-3). *JAMA*. 2016;315(8):801-10.
- Usman O, et al. Comparison of SIRS, qSOFA, and NEWS for the early identification of sepsis in the Emergency Department. *Am J Emerg Med*. 2018.
- Goulden R, Hoyle MC, Monis J, et al. qSOFA, SIRS and NEWS for predicting in hospital mortality and ICU admission in emergency admissions treated as sepsis. *Emerg Med J*. 2018;35(6):345-349.
- Arora S, Singh P, Singh PM, Trikha A. Procalcitonin Levels in Survivors and Nonsurvivors of Sepsis: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Shock*. 2015;43(3):212-21.
- Kim SJ, Hwang SO, Kim YW, Lee JH, Cha KC. Procalcitonin as a diagnostic marker for sepsis/septic shock in the emergency department; a study based on Sepsis-3 definition. *Am J Emerg Med*. 2019;37(2):272-276.
- Self WH, Semler MW, Wanderer JP, et al; SALT-ED Investigators. Balanced Crystalloids versus Saline in Noncritically Ill Adults. *N Engl J Med*. 2018 Mar 1;378(9):819-828.
- Semler MW, Self WH, Wanderer JP, et al; SMART Investigators and the Pragmatic Critical Care Research Group. Balanced Crystalloids versus Saline in Critically Ill Adults. *N Engl J Med*. 2018 Mar 1;378(9):829-839.
- Williams EL, Hildebrand KL, McCormick SA, Bedel MJ. The effect of intravenous lactated Ringer's solution versus 0.9% sodium chloride solution on serum osmolality in human volunteers. *Anesth Analg*. 1999;88(5):999-1003.
- Lobo DN, Awad S. Should chloride-rich crystalloids remain the mainstay of fluid resuscitation to prevent 'pre-renal' acute kidney injury?: con. *Kidney Int*. 2014;86(6):1096-105.

References

- Levy, M., Evans, L. and Rhodes, A. The Surviving Sepsis Campaign Bundle: 2018 update. *Intensive Care Med*, 2018;44: 925.
- Green RS, Djogovic D, Gray S, et al. Canadian Association of Emergency Physicians Sepsis Guidelines: the optimal management of severe sepsis in Canadian emergency departments. *CJEM*. 2008;10(5):443-59.
- Yealy DM, Kellum JA, Huang DT, et al. A randomized trial of protocol-based care for early septic shock. *N Engl J Med*. 2014;370(18):1683-93.
- Jiang LB, Zhang M, Jiang SY, Ma YF. Early goal-directed resuscitation for patients with severe sepsis and septic shock: a meta-analysis and trial sequential analysis. *Scand J Trauma Resusc Emerg Med*. 2016;24:23.
- Mouncey, P et al. Trial of Early, Goal-Directed Resuscitation for Septic Shock. *N Engl J Med* 2015; 372:1301-1311.
- Corl KA, George NR, Romanoff J, et al. Inferior vena cava collapsibility detects fluid responsiveness among spontaneously breathing critically-ill patients. *J Crit Care*. 2017;41:130-137.
- Hernández G, Ospina-tascón GA, Damiani LP, et al. Effect of a Resuscitation Strategy Targeting Peripheral Perfusion Status vs Serum Lactate Levels on 28-Day Mortality Among Patients With Septic Shock: The ANDROMEDA-SHOCK Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA*. 2019;321(7):654-664.
- De azevedo JR, Torres OJ, Beraldi RA, Ribas CA, Malafaia O. Prognostic evaluation of severe sepsis and septic shock: procalcitonin clearance vs Δ Sequential Organ Failure Assessment. *J Crit Care*. 2015;30(1):219.e9-12.

References

- Permpikul C, Tongyoo S, Viarasilpa T, Trainarongsakul T, Chakorn T, Udompanturak S. Early Use of Norepinephrine in Septic Shock Resuscitation (CENSER) : A Randomized Trial. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2019;Feb 1.
- Self WH, Semler MW, Bellomo R, et al. Liberal Versus Restrictive Intravenous Fluid Therapy for Early Septic Shock: Rationale for a Randomized Trial. *Ann Emerg Med*. 2018;72(4):457-466.
- Kim WY, Jun JH, Huh JW, Hong SB, Lim CM, Koh Y. Radial to femoral arterial blood pressure differences in septic shock patients receiving high-dose norepinephrine therapy. *Shock*. 2013;40(6):527-31.
- Gordon AC, Mason AJ, Thirunavukkarasu N, et al. Effect of Early Vasopressin vs Norepinephrine on Kidney Failure in Patients With Septic Shock: The VANISH Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA*. 2016;316(5):509-18.
- Russell JA, Walley KR, Singer J, et al. Vasopressin versus norepinephrine infusion in patients with septic shock. *N Engl J Med*. 2008;358(9):877-87.
- Sanghvi S, Podlog M, Aycock RD. Does the Severe Sepsis and Septic Shock Early Management Bundle (SEP-1) Improve Survival in Septic Adults?. *Ann Emerg Med*. 2018.
- Kumar A, Ellis P, Arabi Y, Roberts D, Light B, Parillo J, et al. Initiation of inappropriate antimicrobial therapy results in a fivefold reduction of survival in human septic shock. *Chest*. 2009;136:1237-48.
- Venkatesh B, Finfer S, Cohen J, et al. Adjunctive Glucocorticoid Therapy in Patients with Septic Shock. *N Engl J Med*. 2018.
- Annane D, Renault A, Brun-buisson C, et al. Hydrocortisone plus Fludrocortisone for Adults with Septic Shock. *N Engl J Med*. 2018;378(9):809-818.
- Marik PE, Khangoora V, Rivera R, Hooper MH, Catravas J. Hydrocortisone, Vitamin C, and Thiamine for the Treatment of Severe Sepsis and Septic Shock: A Retrospective Before-After Study. *Chest*. 2017;151(6):1229-1238.